

The Effect of Maintenance Department Performance and Service Quality of Offshore Vessel on Increased Charterer Satisfaction

(Study Case at PT. Baruna Raya Logistics)

Azzyra Hana Paramadiena ^{a,1}, Asep Suparman ^{b,2}, Endang Sugiharti ^{b,3}
^{a,b} Institut Transportasi dan Logistik Trisakti, Jakarta Indonesia

Abstract:- PT. Baruna Raya Logistics is a company engaged in providing ship services specifically for offshore drilling sites. However, in the performance of the Maintenance Department, there are still several obstacles that can affect the quality of offshore ship services. Service quality is one of the important factors to shape and increase customer satisfaction. This study aims to determine the effect of maintenance department performance and the quality of offshore ship services on increasing customer satisfaction at PT. Baruna Raya Logistics. The research was conducted at PT. Baruna Raya Logistics using quantitative descriptive method, with path analysis with the number of research samples taken as many as 34 respondents to ship users according to the number of ships owned by the company called census sampling. Data were collected through the instrument in the form of statement sheets which were tested using SPSS software version.24. With the results of the study that there is a positive and significant effect of the performance of the maintenance department and the quality of service on customer satisfaction partially or simultaneously. Then it can be known things that need to be done or improved by the company.

Keywords:- Maintenance Department Performance, Service Quality, Increasing Customer Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

PT. Baruna Raya Logistics is a company engaged in the provision of ships specifically provided for crew transportation, security patrols, chase boats or logistics transportation survey needs to offshore drilling sites, having a fleet of 34 ships. Fleet customers of PT. Baruna Raya Logistics is referred to as a charterer or tenant. The charterer will use the ship according to the needs of PT. Baruna Raya Logistics is a Time Charter type, where the rental is calculated based on the time of use of the ship. Rental fees can be calculated on a monthly, weekly or daily basis. Where the human resources who manage and ensure that the repair, maintenance and docking work of the ship is carried out efficiently, controlled and effectively by maintaining adequate record keeping is called the Performance Maintenance Department. Purnomo, Wahyudi, & Suprayitno (2016) identified that performance is a description of the level of achievement of the implementation of an activity/program/policy in realizing the goals, objectives,

vision, and mission of the organization contained in the planning strategy of an organization.

However, in his work there are obstacles such as the ship being used or rented experiencing problems because the ship owned by PT. Baruna Raya Logistics is old, so it can affect the quality of ship services such as engine damage, electrical damage that requires the ship to be docked or the condition of the ship that must be repaired immediately, so the company must send a backup ship to replace the problematic ship. When the company has to send a reserve ship, there is not always a reserve ship available due to other needs and needs on the reserve ship.

Other problems also exist such as inaccuracy in the required documents, so it will take more time which has an impact on the tenant, and can result in the company so that it can be given a warning or up to a penalty. There are also ships that will dock in 2019 which can affect the operational activities of other ships.

The problems experienced by the ship several times also necessitated bringing in the need for spare parts and mechanics from abroad due to the occurrence of repairs to parts of the ship that were not predictable before so that they did not have spare parts in the warehouse and the lack of mechanical ability of the company PT. Baruna Raya Logistics to complete ship repairs, so that ship repairs will take even longer time. In today's highly competitive situation, companies are required to be able and able to develop and improve the quality of services even better, and be able to innovate both the goods and services produced.

The ability to provide quality goods and services is closely related to customer needs and wants. Companies that are able to understand the needs and desires of their customers well are expected to provide a level of satisfaction for customers while at the same time overcoming competitors. By using the theory of performance as an independent variable, it is different from previous research which did not use.

This study aims to determine the effect of maintenance department performance and service quality of offshore vessels on customer satisfaction partially or simultaneously at PT. Baruna Raya Logistics.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research approach is quantitative to describe the effect of maintenance department performance and service quality partially or simultaneously on customer satisfaction, while previous research is quantitative descriptive. Data was collected through field research, observation, and library research. Data were collected through the instrument in the form of statement sheets which were tested using SPSS software version.25. The data analysis technique in this study uses multiple regression correlation, and hypothesis testing through t-test and F-test, with a total population of 34 ship users according to the number of ships owned by the company and the entire population will be used as a sample, called the saturated sample.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Data respondents' data were classified based on:

Jenis Kelamin	Jumlah Responden	Persentase (%)
Laki – laki	17	50%
Perempuan	17	50%
TOTAL	34	100%

Sumber: data diolah oleh penulis

Table 1 Respondent Data by Gender

Usia (Tahun)	Jumlah Responden	Persentase (%)
≤30 Tahun	8	23.5%
31 – 40 Tahun	19	55.9%
41 – 50 Tahun	6	17.6%
≥ 51 Tahun	1	2.9%
TOTAL	34	100%

Sumber: data diolah oleh penulis

Table 2 Respondent Data by Age

Lama Bekerja	Jumlah Responden	Persentase (%)
≤5 Tahun	10	29.4%
6 – 10 Tahun	19	55.9%
11 – 20 Tahun	4	11.8%
≥ 21 Tahun	1	2.9%
TOTAL	34	100%

Sumber: data diolah oleh penulis

Table 3 Respondent Data Based on Length of Work

➤ *Questionnaire Results*

Collecting data by giving statements to respondents using a Likert scale shows the results of the highest and lowest statements of each variable, namely:

Butir no.	Pernyataan	Σ	Bobot	Rata-rata Bobot Penilaian
TERTINGGI				
1	PT. Baruna Raya Logistics memiliki jumlah karyawan/crew di kantor yang memadai.	34	145	4.26
TERENDAH				
3	PT. Baruna Raya Logistics memiliki karyawan/crew yang menguasai kemampuan perbaikan/pemeliharaan kapal dengan baik.	34	122	3.59

Table 4 Results of the Recapitulation of the Maintenance Department Performance Variable Questionnaire (X1)

The statement with the highest weight and average value is found in the 1 (one) statement item with a weight of 145 and an average of 4.26, which means that PT. Baruna Raya Logistics has an adequate number of employees/crew in the office.

The statement with the lowest weight and average value is in the 3rd (three) statement item with a weight of 122 and an average of 3.59, which means that the employees of PT. Baruna Raya Logistics lack the ability to repair/maintain ships well.

Butir no.	Pernyataan	Σ	Bobot	Rata-rata Bobot Penilaian
TERTINGGI				
5	PT. Baruna Raya Logistics memiliki crew yang menguasai metode-metode keselamatan kerja dengan baik.	34	156	4.59
TERENDAH				
9	PT. Baruna Raya Logistics memiliki kondisi armada kapal yang terpelihara dengan baik.	34	111	3.26

Table 5 Results of the Questionnaire Recapitulation of Service Quality Variables (X2)

The statement with the highest weight and average value is in the 5th (five) statement item with a weight of 156 and an average of 4.59, which means that PT. Baruna Raya Logistics provides a sense of security as a sign of service quality on good guarantees to charterers.

The statement with the lowest weight and average value is in the 9th (ninth) statement item with a weight of 111 and an average of 3.26, which means that the ship owned by PT. Baruna Raya Logistics is not well maintained due to the factor of the ship being old.

Butir no.	Pernyataan	Σ	Bobot	Rata-rata Bobot Penilaian
TERTINGGI				
2	Pelanggan merasa puas dengan ketersediaan dan kelayakan alat-alat keselamatan pada kapal milik PT. Baruna Raya Logistics	34	149	4.38
TERENDAH				
5	Pelanggan merasa puas dengan pelayanan yang diberikan PT. Baruna Raya Logistics	34	134	3.94

Table 7 Results of Questionnaire Recapitulation of Customer Satisfaction Variables (Y)

The statement with the highest weight and average value is in the 2 (two) statement item with a weight of 149 and an average of 4.38, which means that PT. Baruna Raya Logistics provides quality products through safety equipment available on board to ensure a sense of security for charterers/ship users to increase customer satisfaction of PT. Baruna Raya Logistics

The respondent's statement with the lowest weight and average value is in the 5th (five) statement item with a weight of 134 and an average of 3.94, which means that PT. Baruna Raya Logistics still has to try to improve employee performance and service quality, because there are many competing companies in the same field.

➤ *Validity Test and Reliability Test*

The validity test was used with the aim of knowing the validity of the questionnaire with the criteria of r arithmetic $>$ r table = valid, (at a significance of 0.05 with and $n = 34$) indicating the value of r table obtained was 0.339. From the test results, each statement item on each variable has r count $>$ r table (0.339), then it is declared valid.

Reliability testing aims to determine the consistency of the questionnaire with Cronbach's Alpha value criteria $>$ 0.600. From the test results, each variable has a Cronbach Alpha value $>$ 0.600, then it is declared reliable.

➤ *Correlation Coefficient Test*

a. The correlation coefficient value between Maintenance Department Performance (X1) and Service Quality (X2) obtained a correlation calculation of 0.467 and shows sufficient influence because it is in the interval 0.400 – 0.599.

		Kinerja Maintenance Department	Kualitas Pelayanan	Kepuasan Pelanggan
Kinerja Maintenance Department	Pearson Correlation	1	.467 [*]	.638 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.033	.000
N		34	34	34
Kualitas Pelayanan	Pearson Correlation	.467 [*]	1	.665 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.033		.000
N		34	34	34
Kepuasan Pelanggan	Pearson Correlation	.638 ^{**}	.665 ^{**}	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
N		34	34	34

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Sumber: data diolah menggunakan IBM SPSS versi 25

Table 8 Correlation Coefficient Test

b. The correlation coefficient value between Maintenance Department Performance (X1) and Customer Satisfaction (Y) obtained a correlation calculation of 0.638 and shows a strong influence because it is in the interval 0.600 – 0.799.

c. The value of the correlation coefficient between Service Quality (X2) on Customer Satisfaction (Y) obtained a correlation calculation of 0.665 and shows a strong influence because it is in the interval 0.600 – 0.799.

Model Summary ^a									
Model	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					
				R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.788 ^a	.621	.597	1.771	.621	25.393	2	31	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Kualitas Pelayanan, Kinerja Maintenance Department
b. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Pelanggan

Table 9 Multiple Correlation Test

The value of the multiple correlation coefficient test, R , is 0.788. This shows that the relationship between Maintenance Department Performance and Service Quality simultaneously on Customer Satisfaction has a strong influence.

➤ *Multiple Linear Regression Test*

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	9.653	4.449		2.170	.038
	Kinerja Maintenance Department	.366	.096	.455	3.826	.001
	Kualitas Pelayanan	.427	.102	.498	4.189	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Pelanggan

Table 10 Multiple Linear Regression Test

The regression equation model can be written in concurrent form as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_n X_n$$

$$Y' = 9.653 + 0.366 X_1 + 0.427 X_2$$

Description :

1. Value of constant a

The value of the constant a is 9.653 which means that if the independent variable is independent or there is no maintenance department performance variable (X1) and service quality (X2), then the influence of customer satisfaction (Y) will be worth 9.653

2. The value of the coefficient b1

The b1 value is 0.366, which means that from the regression equation it can be seen that the performance of the maintenance department (X1) on customer satisfaction (Y) is in the same direction (positive), which is shown in the regression equation with a positive number of 0.366.

3. The value of the coefficient b2

The b2 value is 0.427, which means that from the regression equation it can be seen that the performance of the maintenance department (X1) on customer satisfaction (Y) is in the positive direction shown in the regression equation with a positive number of 0.427.

$$dk = N - K$$

$$dk = 34 - 2$$

$$dk = 32 = 2.037$$

➤ Hypothesis testing

t Test

1. **H1**, The Effect of Variable X1 (Maintenance Department Performance) on Variable X2 (Service Quality)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	26.756	6.101		4.385	.000
	Kinerja Maintenance Department	.345	.155	.467	2.232	.033

a. Dependent Variable: Kualitas Pelayanan

Sumber: data diolah menggunakan IBM SPSS versi 25

Table 11 Test Test Results (H1)

From the partial test, it can be obtained on the X1 variable (Maintenance Department Performance) to X2 (Service Quality) variable where it is known that the significance level is 0.033 and the t count is 2.232. From the number of respondents (n) as many as 34 people, it can be obtained that the t table is 2,037. Obtained based on the formula:

From this data, the following results are obtained:

- 0.033 < 0.05 , then Ho is rejected Ha is accepted.
- 2.232 > 2.037 , then Ho is rejected Ha is accepted.

It can be concluded that there is a significant effect between Variable X1 (Performance of Maintenance Department) on Variable X2 (Quality of Service).

Figure 2 Normal Curve t-test Variable X1 to Variable X2

Thus, the initial hypothesis is that there is a significant and positive effect between Variable X1 and Variable X2.

2. **H2**, Effect of Variable X1 (Performance of Maintenance Department) on Variable Y (Customer Satisfaction)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	9.653	4.449		2.170	.038
	Kinerja Maintenance Department	.366	.096	.455	3.826	.001
	Kualitas Pelayanan	.427	.102	.498	4.189	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Pelanggan

Table 12 T-Test Test Results (H2)

From the partial test can be obtained on the variable X1 (Maintenance Department Performance) to Variable Y (Customer Satisfaction) where it is known that the significance level is 0.001 and t count is 3.826. From the number of respondents (n) as many as 34 people, it can be obtained that the t table is 2,037. Obtained based on the formula:

From this data, the following results are obtained:

$$dk = N - K$$

$$dk = 34 - 2$$

$$dk = 32 = 2.037$$

- 0.001 < 0.05 , then Ho is rejected Ha is accepted.
- 3.826 > 2.037 , then Ho is rejected, Ha is accepted.

It can be concluded that there is a significant effect between Variable X1 (Maintenance Department Performance) on Variable Y (Customer Satisfaction).

Figure 3. Normal Curve t-test Variable X1 to Variable Y

Thus, the initial hypothesis is that there is a significant and positive effect between Variable X1 on Variable Y.

3. **H3**, The Effect of Variable X2 (Service Quality) on Variable Y (Customer Satisfaction)

$$F_{t_{tabel}} = n - k - 1$$

$$F_{t_{tabel}} = 34 - 2 - 1$$

$$F_{t_{tabel}} = 31 = 3.30$$

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	d		
1	(Constant)	9.653	4.449		2.170	.038
	Kinerja Maintenance Department	.366	.096	.455	3.826	.001
	Kualitas Pelayanan	.427	.102	.498	4.189	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Pelanggan

Table 13 Results of the t-test (H3)

From the partial test, it can be obtained on the X2 (Service Quality) variable to Y (Customer Satisfaction) variable where it is known that the significance level is 0.000 and the t count is 4.189. From the number of respondents (n) as many as 34 people, it can be obtained that the t table is 2,037. Obtained based on the formula:

From this data, the following results are obtained:

$$dk = N - K$$

$$dk = 34 - 2$$

$$dk = 32 = 2.037$$

0.000 < 0.05 then Ho is rejected, Ha is accepted.
4.189 > 2.03 then Ho is rejected Ha is accepted.

It can be concluded that there is a significant effect between Variable X2 (Service Quality) on Variable Y (Customer Satisfaction).

Fig 4 Normal Curve t-test Variable X2 to Variable Y

Thus, the initial hypothesis is that there is a significant and positive effect between Variable X2 on Variable Y.

➤ *F Uji test*

The F test tested the variables simultaneously (simultaneously) between all independent variables (Maintenance Department Performance and Service Quality) on the dependent variable (Customer Satisfaction). Table 14 F Test Results (H4)

The data above is obtained from the regression analysis carried out by the author and it is known that the Ftable obtained from the formula:

From the formula it can be concluded that:

0.000 < 0.05, then Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted.
25.393 > 3.30, then Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted.

So it can be said that Variable X1 (Performance of Maintenance Department) and Variable X2 (Quality of Service) simultaneously have a significant and positive effect on Variable Y (Customer Satisfaction).

Fig 5 Normal Curve of F-Test Variables X1 and X2 against Y

The initial hypothesis was obtained that there was a significant positive effect between variable X1 (Performance of Maintenance Department) and Variable X2 (Quality of Service) simultaneously on Variable Y (Customer Satisfaction).

IV. DISCUSSION

➤ **H1**, *influence between Maintenance Department Performance on Service Quality*

Maintenance Department performance has a positive and significant impact on service quality. Based on the results of the analysis, the path coefficient of maintenance department performance on service quality is 0.467 or 46.7% with a significance of 0.033, it can be said that the relationship between the performance of maintenance department performance on service quality is quite influential (in the interval 0.400 – 0.599). Which means that the more employees or crew master the ability to repair and maintain ships well, the ships have a good condition (seaworthy) to operate according to the time schedule that has been determined to be rented to charterers. Because timeliness is one of the factors that can affect the quality of service to charters/tenants.

➤ **H2**, *influence between Maintenance Department Performance on Customer Satisfaction*

The performance of the Maintenance Department has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. Based on the results of the analysis, the path coefficient of maintenance department performance on customer satisfaction is 0.665 or 66.5% with a significance of 0.001, it can be said that the relationship between maintenance department performance and customer satisfaction is strong (in the interval 0.600 – 0.799). This means that timeliness is also something that affects customer satisfaction, where the punctuality of the departure/arrival of ships and the availability of spare parts for goods needed for repair and maintenance of ships and the availability of spare ships if needed at any time if the ship is being chartered by the charterer experienced problems such as engine damage/breakdown due to the age of the ship owned by PT. Baruna Raya Logistics averages over 30 years.

➤ **H3**, *the influence of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction*

Service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. Based on the results of the analysis, the path coefficient of maintenance department performance on customer satisfaction is 0.638 or 63.8% with a significance of 0.000, it can be said that the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction is strong (in the interval 0.600 – 0.799). Which means that work discipline, thoroughness and responsiveness are very much needed in handling complaints and problems that occur such as documents that have not been issued / reported which result in delays in sending ships not on time. The results of this study are in accordance with previous research by Hudi, Suhirman (2006), namely the analysis of the effect of the quality of offshore ship services on customer/user satisfaction.

➤ **H4**, *Effect of Maintenance Department Performance and Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction*

Kinerja Maintenance Department dan Kualitas Pelayanan secara simultan berpengaruh positif dan signifikan terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan. Berdasarkan hasil analisis,

diperoleh koefisien jalur kinerja maintenance department dan kualitas pelayanan terhadap kepuasan pelanggan sebesar 0.788 atau 78.8% dengan signifikansi 0.001, dapat dikatakan bahwa hubungan pengaruh kinerja maintenance department terhadap kepuasan pelanggan adalah kuat (berada pada interval 0.600 – 0.799). Ini berarti bahwa dalam meningkatkan kepuasan pelanggan, pihak ownership atau perusahaan harus meningkatkan kualitas armada seperti kemampuan daya tahan armada, kebersihan armada, memperhatikan fasilitas keselamatan baik jumlah, kelengkapan dan kualitas perawatannya, serta keterampilan crew dalam menangani pemeliharaan/perbaikan kapal dan ketelitian dalam mengurus dokumen yang dibutuhkan, keramahan serta cepat tanggap dalam menangani keluhan bila terjadi masalah pada kapal yang disewa dan dapat segera menemukan solusi terbaik. Hasil penelitian ini sesuai dengan penelitian terdahulu Hudi, Suhirman (2006) yaitu analisis pengaruh kualitas layanan jasa kapal lepas pantai terhadap kepuasan pelanggan/pengguna.

V. CONCLUSION

From the results of research and analysis as a whole, it can be concluded as follows:

- The performance of the maintenance department has a positive and significant effect on service quality. Based on the results of the analysis, the results obtained that the performance of the maintenance department on the service quality of PT. Baruna Raya Logistics is 0.467 or 46.7% with a significance of 0.033. This means that if employees in the maintenance department further increase their knowledge and ability in ship repair and maintenance, they will be able to improve the quality of company services.
- The performance of the maintenance department has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. Based on the results of the analysis, the results obtained that the performance of the maintenance department on customer satisfaction is 0.665 or 66.5% with a significance of 0.001.
- This means that if the ship's departure/arrival delivery to the charterer can always be on time, the charterer will be satisfied with the company's on time performance.
- The quality of services provided by PT. Baruna Raya Logistics has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. Based on the results obtained that the service quality of PT. Baruna Raya Logistics on customer satisfaction is 0.638 or 63.8% with a significance of 0.000. This means that if employees are always thorough, disciplined, responsive and friendly in serving charterers/customers, the charterers/customers will be satisfied with the services provided by the company.
- Performance of maintenance department and service quality of PT. Baruna Raya Logistics simultaneously has a positive effect and significant to customer satisfaction. Based on the results of the analysis, the results obtained simultaneously that is equal to 0.788 or 78.8% with a significance of 0.000. This means that with many similar rival companies, PT. Baruna Raya Logistics needs to improve its performance and service quality to achieve customer satisfaction, customers who are satisfied with

the services provided will use the services of PT. Baruna Raya Logistics is back, called customer loyalty.

SUGGESTION

- In the Maintenance Department Performance variable (X1), it shows that PT. Baruna Raya Logistics has an adequate number of office employees, but the employees/crew in the maintenance sector show that they lack the ability to repair/maintain ships properly. This can affect the completion time of ship repair/maintenance which also results in the company needing to use mechanics from abroad. So that it is necessary to increase the ability of these employees, among others, by conducting training which is expected to increase the ability of employees to complete ship repairs and maintenance.
- The variable of Service Quality (X2) shows that PT. Baruna Raya Logistics has a crew that is well versed in work safety methods, but shows that the condition of the ship is not well maintained. This is due to the age of the ship which can be said to be old so that several times there have been unpredicted ship damage, so it is necessary to have a controlled inspection of the ship and a record of spare parts inventory to be available in the company's warehouse so that ships that are under repair/maintenance do not have to wait any longer. PT. Baruna Raya Logistics must also send a replacement ship to replace the damaged ship to the charterer.
- The Customer Satisfaction variable (Y) shows that the charterers are satisfied with the availability and feasibility of PT. Baruna Raya Logistics, but there are still things that affect customer satisfaction in its services. Such as the inaccuracy of employees in handling the required documents, responsive service in handling customer complaints and problems, while still prioritizing politeness, aiming to provide peace to customers who complain/experience problems on the chartered ship.
- On the variable of Maintenance Department Performance (X1) and Service Quality (X2) simultaneously on Customer Satisfaction (Y), based on the problems found in each of the variables above and the weaknesses of the company namely on the age of the fleet such as the endurance of the fleet and the condition of the ship which is not good. Some of these things become evaluation materials or comparisons for customers with many competing companies in similar fields. So companies need to improve such as morale, and the integration of every employee in order to compete with other rival companies.

The following are some of the implications considered relevant to the study. These implications include the following:

The need for training - training that uses training methods with integrated materials which are expected to improve the capabilities and performance of employees and the quality of service PT. Baruna Raya Logistics to provide services quickly and precisely in handling customer complaints while still prioritizing friendliness and politeness

of service which aims to increase customer satisfaction. There is also a need for positive encouragement or motivation that is given effectively by superiors to employees, aiming to be able to improve the performance of the spirit of their employees.

If the training needed regularly and effectively with the aim of improving the performance of the maintenance department and the quality of service is not met by the company, it will have implications for customer satisfaction. If there are things that can harm the company by the charterer due to disappointment that the charterer's needs and expectations are not fulfilled, then PT. Baruna Raya Logistics must explore and improve its core competency in order to be able to compete with other similar companies so that it has a reputation that is taken into account and considered for every customer in making choices.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Desan, Henriawan,. 2015, November. *Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan dan Kepuasan Pelanggan Terhadap Loyalitas Pelanggan. Copetition*, Vol. VI, No. 2
- [2]. Hudi, Suhirman. 2006. *Analisis Pengaruh Kualitas Layanan Jasa Kapal Lepas Pantai Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan/Pengguna Armada Pada PT. Baruna Raya Logistics*. (Tesis). Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Kampus Ungu.
- [3]. Ishak, A., & Lutfi. 2011. *Pengaruh Kepuasan dan Kepercayaan Konsumen Terhadap Loyalitas : Studi Tentaannng Peran Mediasi Switching Costs*. Jurnal Siasat Bisnis Vol. 15 No. 1, Januari 2011 55 – 66.
- [4]. Mahendra, B. A. 2018. *Pentingnya Pelaksanaan Docking Untuk Menjaga Kelaiklautan Kapal Pada Mv. Energy Prosperity*.
- [5]. Majid, S. A. 2015. *Customer Service Dalam Bisnis Jasa Transportasi* (Edisi ke 4). PT. RAJAGRAFINDO PERSADA.
- [6]. Minrohayati., Meirani., dan Sri, Lestari. 2016. *Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan Terhadap Loyalitas Pelanggan Pada Toko Buku Online Universitas Tebuka*. Jurnal Manajemen Indonesia Vol.16 - No.3 Desember 2016
- [7]. Musa, Kasuar Kuka Gambo. 2016. *Service Quality And Customer Satisfaction Among Domestic Air Passengers In Nigeria*. International Journal Of Business And Management Studies Vol 8, No 2, 2016 Issn: 1309-8047 (Online).
- [8]. Nur, Ririn., & Siti, Hadijah. 2016, Agustus. *Peningkatan Kinerja Pegawai Melalui Kepuasan Kerja dan Disiplin Kerja*. Jurnal Pendidikan Manajemen Perkantoran Vol. 1, No. 1, 204 – 214.
- [9]. Rahayu, Purwanti. 2017. *Hubungan Keterlambatan Crew Boarding dan Maintenance Non-Schedule dengan On Time Pperformance PT. Citilink Indonesia*. Institut Transportasi dan Logistik Trisakti.
- [10]. Rohaeni, H., & Marwa, Nisa,. 2018, September. *Kualitas Pelayanan Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan*. Jurnal Ecodemica Vol. 2, No. 2.

- [11]. Sonhaji. 2018. *Pemberian Surat Persetujuan Berlayar (SPB) dalam Upaya Pemenuhan Keselamatan Berlayar*. Administrative Law & Governance Journal. Vol. 1 Edisi 3 Agustus 2018
- [12]. Sugiyono. (2012). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan Kombinasi (Mixed Methods)*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- [13]. Indonesia, Undang – Undang Nomor 17 Tahun 2018 Tentang Pelayaran
- [14]. Yanuar, M. 2017. *Pengaruh Motivasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. Laju Perdana Indah Dengan Kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Mediasi*. (Tesis). Universitas Lampung.
- [15]. Yoga, Iswari. 2021. *Prosedur Penanganan Dokumen Kapal Clearance In Dan Clearance Out Di Ksop Kelas 1 Sorong*. Karya Tulis. Universitas Maritim AMNI Semarang.